

NOTES

Among all the 2-imidazoline derivatives only four compounds are inactive against *S. aureus* and the rest are active. Many compounds were found active against *S. aureus* in comparison to *E. coli*. Only two compounds were active against *E. coli* having substitution 6-bromobenzthiazolyl and 4-chlorophenylthiazolyl to imidazole ring and the others found inactive against the same gram -ve bacteria.

The same 2-imidazoline derivatives were screened for antitubercular activity against H_{87Rv} strain of *M. tuberculosis*. Only two compounds having substitution 6-sulphonamidobenzthiazolyl and 4-methylphenylthiazolyl to the imidazole ring were found active at lower concentration (10 µg ml⁻¹), five compounds active at higher concentration (100 µg ml⁻¹) and two compounds active at both the concentrations (Table 1).

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Mannich Bases of Ethyl 5-Substituted-benzimidazole-2-thioacetate and their Anti-inflammatory and Analgesic Activities

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WIDE range of biological activities¹ are reported with various benzimidazole compounds. Some benzimidazole-2-thiones, 1,3-disubstituted benzimidazole-2-thiones and thioesters are reported to exhibit analgesic and antiinflammatory activities².

The title compounds were thus prepared for evaluating their analgesic and antiinflammatory activity.

The benzimidazole-2-thiones and their 5-substituted analogues were synthesised by the reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine or 4-substituted-*o*-phenylenediamine using CS₂ in presence of ethanolic KOH³. Their corresponding 2-thioacetic acid ethyl ester was prepared using chloroacetic acid, KOH, ethanol and HCl gas.

The title compounds (2) were obtained from 1 by reacting with various amines in presence of aqueous 40% formaldehyde solution following standard procedure of Mannich reaction.

R = H, CH₃, OC₂H₅.

R' = *N*-Morpholine, *N*-Piperidine,

N,N-Dibutyl, *N,N*-Dicyclohexyl

A mixture of 1 (0.01 mol) was taken in methanol (50 ml) and to it formalin (40% aqueous, 0.02 mol) was added followed by the secondary amine (0.01 mol) with stirring for 3 h. The solvent was evaporated on a water-bath to get a crude product. It was decolourised by refluxing with activated charcoal in methanol and crystallised from methanol-acetone mixture.

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 377 spectrophotometer; $\nu_{\max}$ 1 170 (C-O stretch for ethoxy), 1 110-1 240 (C-O-C), 1 180-1 200 (C=S) and 1 385 cm⁻¹ (CCH₃). Uv spectra (EtOH) were recorded on a Ultrospec 4050 spectrophotometer (Table 1). The elemental analyses were carried out at N.S.I.C., Nagpur and the C and H data were found satisfactory. The purity and homogeneity of the compounds were checked by tlc. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Analgesic activity: The activity of compounds was determined by writhing method⁴. A group of albino mice of either sex, weighing 20-24 g were used. Suspension of the compounds and aspirin (standard drug) was prepared in 10% Tween-80 and were administered at 30 mg/kg does (150 mg/kg for aspirin) intraperitoneally. After 30 min later 300 mg/kg of 3% acetic acid was administered to each animal and writhing recorded for 20 min. The

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL, SPECTRAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF COMPOUND 3*

R	R'	Yield %	M.p. °C	Mol. formula	$\lambda_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	% oedema inhibition*	% protection against writhing*
H	N-Morpholine	35.2	110–111	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	318	56.32	45.55
H	N-Piperidine	37.7	135–136	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	320	68.28	48.79
H	N,N-Dibutyl	33.6	237–239	C ₂₀ H ₃₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	308	64.36	42.37
H	N,N-Dicyclohexyl	30.3	203–205	C ₂₄ H ₃₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	311	62.48	40.53
OC ₂ H ₅	N-Morpholine	39.3	98–100	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	317	70.32	57.02
OC ₂ H ₅	N-Piperidine	40.1	118–119	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	319	76.41	66.66
OC ₂ H ₅	N,N-Dibutyl	37.7	213–215	C ₂₂ H ₃₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	310	68.56	60.33
OC ₂ H ₅	N,N-Dicyclohexyl	36.5	198–201	C ₂₆ H ₃₇ N ₂ O ₂ S	322	64.20	53.70
CH ₃	N-Morpholine	34.9	119–121	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₂ O ₂ S	321	65.81	52.38
CH ₃	N-Piperidine	35.8	126–128	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	319	69.23	63.80
CH ₃	N,N-Dibutyl	32.6	193–195	C ₂₁ H ₃₁ N ₂ O ₂ S	314	60.12	57.66
CH ₃	N,N-Dicyclohexyl	31.0	177–179	C ₂₅ H ₃₅ N ₂ O ₂ S	316	58.84	50.27
Indomethacin						90.32	—
Aspirin						—	87.28

*Coefficient of variation was within 1.5 to 3.6%.

analgesic activity was measured in terms of percentage protection,

$$\% \text{ Protection} = 100 - (D/C \times 100)$$

where, *D* is average writhing response for compound tested and *C* the average writhing response for control (Table 1).

Antiinflammatory activity: The activity was measured by carragenan induced rat paw oedema method⁶ using digital plethysmometer. Young albino rats weighing 100–200 g of either sex were used. A group of five animals was taken for testing at one dose level. One group was employed as control, while to two groups indomethacin (10 mg/kg) was given as standard drug. A 10% Tween-80 for control and suspension of test compounds at 30 and 10 mg/kg in 10% Tween-80 were injected intraperitoneally. After 20 min, carragenan (200 mcg/rat) was injected into planter tissue of right hind paw of rats of each group and the increase in paw volume was recorded. After 3 h inhibition of inflammation, if any, was measured by recording rat paw volume. Antiinflammatory activity was measured in terms of % inhibition of oedema,

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{V_0 - V_t}{V_0} \times 100$$

where, *V*₀ and *V*_t are average increase in paw volume of control and test animal, respectively. The results are recorded in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds tested for analgesic and antiinflammatory activities showed promising results. 5-Ethoxy-1,3-dipiperidinomethylethyl-2-benzimidazole thioacetate showed potent analgesic and antiinflammatory activities. Amongst the others, compounds having 5-ethoxy as substituent showed good analgesic activity. Mannich bases with morpholine and piperidine as substituents seemed to have analgesic-antiinflammatory activities.

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Synthesis of some New Isonicotinoylazopyrazoles

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SULPHA drugs are well known for their various physiological activity¹⁻³. Isoniazid is an established antitubercular drug. In the light of the importance of sulpha drugs, isoniazid and considering the biological activity exhibited by azo group, it was considered worthwhile to combine the sulpha drugs with isoniazid through azo group in order to